

TRANSLATION OF TEXT TYPES OF VARIOUS GENRES AND STYLES

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Abstract. This article is devoted to translation of texts and their types of various genres and styles. In addition, it gives information about features of the most common text types and their translations in English language.

Key words: types of text, genres, narrative texts, expository texts, descriptive and persuasive texts.

ПЕРЕВОД ТЕКСТОВ РАЗЛИЧНЫХ ЖАНРОВ И СТИЛЕЙ

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена переводу текстов и их видов различных жанров и стилей. Кроме того, дается информация об особенностях наиболее распространенных типов текста и их переводах на английский язык.

Ключевые слова: типы текста, жанры, тексты-нарративы, описательные тексты, описательные и убеждающие тексты.

Depending upon their purpose, different texts have specific styles and structures. The groups of styles and structures are called text types. Depending on what your purpose is, you must be able to choose an appropriate text type and follow its genre conventions. Text types are generally semantic and functional concepts and are not to be confused with text forms. Text types, also known as genres or text forms, refer to categories of texts with different purposes. Depending on the purpose, each type of text will have a different convention of style and structure. For example, one of text type is narrative texts and it is type of writing that tells us a story or recounts of events.

Also texts can be written belong to their styles and structures. Based on their genres, generic structure and language feature dominantly used, texts are divided into various types. They are narrative, descriptive, expository, persuasive and report, explanation, procedure, discussion and so on. However, the main writing types are narrative, persuasive, expository and descriptive.

Here, the question is that what is the genre?

The notion of genre is described by Trosborg as text category readily distinguished by mature speakers of a language. According to Miller, a rhetorically sound definition of genre must be centred not on the substance or form of the discourse but on the action it is used to accomplish.

Genre can be recognised as a system for achieving social purposes by verbal means. Therefore, for example guidebooks, poems, business letters, newspaper articles can be referred to as genres because they are used in a particular situation for a particular purpose. The notion of genre refers to completed texts. However, communicative function and text type, which constitute text properties, cut across genres. Hence, informative texts include newspaper reports, textbooks, TV news, also argumentative texts - debates, newspaper articles, political speeches, etc.

According to the framework associated with Aristotle and Bühler, a text can be classified into a particular type according to which of the four components in the communication process

receives the primary focus: speaker, listener, thing referred to or the linguistic material. If the main focus is on the speaker (sender), the text will be expressive; if on the listener (receiver), it will be persuasive; if on the linguistic code, it will be literary (for example, narrative); and if the aim is to represent the realities of the world, it will be referential. Hatim and Mason, therefore, defined text types as a conceptual framework which enables us to classify texts in terms of communicative intentions serving an overall rhetorical purpose. For translation purposes they adopted Werlich's (1976) typology which comprises five text types: description, narration, exposition, argumentation and instruction. In addition, an argumentative text type may be realised by means of narration, instructions - by description.

Narrative texts

Narrative text purpose is to telling the story to the reader. It is not always about telling story for entertainment, though. Besides that, aim of these type of texts lie in its capacity to engage the reader's imagination and just simply pass on a tale through generations. For instance narrative stories are used in literature, also folklore and folktales to pass-on cultural values and stories.

Narrative texts have to do with real world events and time. They may be fictional (fairy tales, novels) and nonfictional (newspaper report). They are characterized by sequencing of events expressed by dynamic verbs and by adverbials such as "and then", "firstly", "second", "third". For example, "Opening it, he discovered that it contained 100 pieces of gold. Then he heard a merchant shouted – Uni ochib, ichida 100 dona oltin borligini aniqladi. Shunda u savdogarning qichqirganini eshitdi."

Descriptive texts

These kind of text is a text that describe the feature of someone, something or a certain place. Descriptive texts is a kind of texts with purpose to give information. For instance, "The construction is began in 1961 under the direction of President Soekarno and the monument was opened to the public in 1975- Qurilish 1961 yilda Prezident Soekarno rahbarligida boshlangan va yodgorlik 1975 yilda jamoatchilikka ochilgan."

Expository texts

Expository text aims to inform or explain, provide the reader with comprehensive information about a specific topic. They include text forms such as definitions, explications, summaries and many type of essay. They may also include text books, non-fiction trade books, newspaper and magazines, directions, essays, speeches, user manuals (how to guides) and government documents (for example, the driver's license test booklet).

Persuasive or argumentative texts

Argumentative texts are an attempt to persuade, or convince others to accept a certain view or take a specific action. It defends a position regarding an issue or topic, using reasoned arguments, facts, statistics, and real-life examples to convince readers and lure them into adopting this point of view.

Persuasive text types include speeches, debates, editor opinion, Blog Post Ads. Persuasive texts use emotive language and rhetorical questions and connecting words and phrases.

For instance, "How would you feel if there were plastic bottles, disposed chemicals, ripped fishing nets and other discarded containers strewn all around your house? - Uyingiz atrofida plastik

butilkalar, utilizatsiya qilingan kimyoviy moddalar, yirtilgan baliq to'rlari va boshqa tashlab ketilgan idishlar bo'lsa, qanday his qilasan a o'zingni?"

Understanding text types helps to effectively communicate ideas and information to our target audience. Additionally, it aids in comprehension, helping readers navigate and understand the text in its intended way. Lastly, knowledge of text types helps improve critical reading skills, enabling readers to discern the underlying purpose and structure of various texts.

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